

MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LEG BONES AND MUSCLES DURING POSTNATAL ONTOGENY OF TURKEYS UNDER DIFFERENT NATURAL CONDITIONS LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract. *These three articles provide information on the changes in leg bones and muscles during the postnatal ontogeny of turkeys, which are causing serious damage to our Republic, based on the literature review.*

Keywords: *turkeys, bones, muscles, metabolism, age of turkeys.*

Аннотация. *В этих трех статьях на основе обзора литературы представлены сведения об изменениях костей и мышц ног в постнатальном онтогенезе индеек, наносящих серьезный ущерб нашей республике.*

Ключевые слова: *индеек, кости, мышцы, метаболизм, возраст индеек.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada Respublikamizga jiddiy zaiyon yetkazayotgan kurkalarning tugʻruqdan keyingi ontogenez davrida oyoq suyaklari va mushaklaridagi oʻzgarishlar haqida adabiyotlar tahlili asosida maʼlumotlar yoritilgan.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *kurka, suyak, muskul, metabolizm, kurkalar yoshi.*

Introduction. Features of the growth of live weight and the mass of individual muscles Intensive production of poultry meat while reducing costs is possible only if their biological characteristics are taken into account. Thus, birds have a high metabolism; therefore, they consume oxygen and emit heat per 1 kg of mass 3-6 times more than mammals.

Keeping and feeding turkeys. Turkeys are raised on the ground in thick beds, cages and camps (groups under shelter). When growing turkeys in thick beds on the ground, the room is disinfected, and the walls of the building are whitewashed with lime. Slaked lime is laid on the floor surface of the rooms with a thickness of 2-4 cm, and wood shavings, straw, straw, crushed corn stalks, rice husks are laid on it with a thickness of 5-6 cm. This method is convenient for use in small poultry farms where turkey meat products are grown [1, 12].

The use of one or another breeding method depends on the breed and crosses of turkeys used in the farm. Light and medium-weight turkey crosses are well adapted to growing in cages. Heavy turkey breeds are grown indoors in thick beds, in most cases in summer camps [10, 11].

The growth of live weight in chickens is influenced by many factors. So, according to A.G. Deblika, the use of probiotics has a beneficial effect on increasing live weight in chickens [2].

Patterns of growth and development of the axial and peripheral skeleton also affect age-related characteristics of live weight gain. In the axial skeleton as a whole and most of its constituent bones, at the beginning of postnatal ontogenesis, the relative mass decreases and then changes in waves. In the peripheral section, on the contrary, an increase in relative mass was first noted, then its change acquired a wave-like character A.B. Kozlov also pointed out the wave-like nature of changes in the relative mass of individual bones and their groups in birds. Ippolitova she

noted that this undulation is clearly expressed in the early periods of bird development and smoothes out towards the end of ontogenesis [3, 4].

Works by M.S. Panueva, E.A. Isaenkova, A.B Kozlova, also devoted to the relationship in the growth of skeletal and muscle mass in meat chickens. As a result of research by E.A. Isaenkova and M.S. Panueva found that the intensity of growth in live weight of chickens decreases with age. Summarizing the data on the study of patterns of growth in the mass of the skeleton and muscles in broiler chickens, we can conclude that in the growth of the mass of bones of the peripheral skeleton and muscles in broiler chickens there are both similar and distinctive features associated with their different functional needs for one or another age span of their lives [5].

Result. Macro morphology of the muscular system. Currently, there is an insufficient amount of literature data on the macromorphology of the muscular system of broiler chickens. Most studies on macromorphology are devoted to the study of the structure of skeletal muscles in humans and animals.

Changes in body weight, long tubular bones of the limbs, muscles of the axial and peripheral skeleton and all organs of the digestive tract, starting from the foregut, were studied in 9 groups of meat chickens, from one day of age to adulthood. The study found that all of them grow with a pattern of decreasing intensity with age. If, for example, during the first week of life of chickens their live weight increased by 3.05 times, then in the sixth week it increased only by 1.29 times. All organ systems studied grew heterochromic. Noteworthy is the fact that uneven growth is inherent not only in different systems of the body and individual organs of the same system, but in different parts of the same organ. Muscle growth occurs spasmodically. During the first two weeks, the “K” of pectoral muscle growth was 7.36; “K” for muscle growth of the pelvic limb - 4.27; thoracic limb - 3.58. Further, the intensity of muscle growth decreases and at the age of two months is 0.82 in the pectoral muscles; 0.94 - for the muscles of the pelvic limb [6].

One of the important indicators of muscle growth is changes in their length and girth. Research results have shown that with age, all muscles increase in length and girth. Moreover, this happens differently in different muscles and at different ages. A more general pattern is that most muscles grow rapidly in length and thickness in the first three weeks of a chicken’s life, and subsequently the intensity of their growth decreases significantly [7].

The problem of adaptation of the body’s musculoskeletal system to a variety of environmental factors, regulation and control of motor activity has been attracting the attention of researchers for four decades. Some researchers: V.E. Gintovt, S.B. Seleznev argued that the muscles of birds are characterized by an extremely uneven distribution on the body. The bulk of it is located in the area of the sternum at the transition to the wing (in chickens it is about 17% of live weight and over 45% of the total muscle mass). The musculature of the thoracolumbar sacral region of chickens, due to low mobility, is poorly developed and accounts for about 1% of live weight and 2% of the weight of all muscles [8].

Solving the problems of rapidly increasing the production of poultry meat and increasing its biological usefulness is possible based on studying age-related changes in the macro and microscopic structure of muscles, the chemical composition and physical properties of the tissues that make up the organs of chicken meat lines [9].

Summary. In his research established the following features in the growth and development of the muscles of chickens:

1. The growth of the pectoral muscles in the first three weeks of postnatal life of chicks occurs more intensively compared to the muscles of the pelvic limb. Under cage-rearing

conditions, the muscle weight of the shoulder girdle, trunk, and neck increases faster than when chickens are kept on the floor.

2. All the muscles studied in the area of the shoulder girdle, thigh and lower leg can be classified into three morpho-functional types: dynamic - both heads of the biceps femoris muscle; dynamo static - both pectoral and intermediate head of the quadriceps femoris muscle; semi-dynamic - the lateral head of the gastrocnemius muscle.

3. The thickness of the muscle fiber depends to a certain extent on the type of muscle. Muscles of the statodynamic and dynamostatic types are thicker than dynamic ones. The muscle fibers of cage-fed chickens are thicker than those of floor-raised chickens.

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